

filtered, washed with cold water, dried and crystallised from ethanol. Yield 23.22 g. (90.00%) m.p. 72°-73°.

(b) *Ethyl-4'-(2-chloro-4-phenylthio-s-triazin-6-yl)-aminobenzoate* (I; $R_1 = Cl$; $R_2 = H_5C_2OOC\ Ph.NH-$; $R_3 = S-C_6H_5$):

Ethyl-4-aminobenzoate (8.250 g.) dissolved in dioxan (25 ml.) was added to the suspension of (compound I; $R_1 = R_1 = Cl$; $R_2 = S-C_6H_5$) (12.90 g.) in dioxan (25 ml.) at 30° to 35°. The contents were stirred for an hour with the gradual addition of an aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml.; 20%) and subsequently poured in crushed ice. The product was isolated as usual and crystallised from ethanol. Yield 18.5 g. (95.72%) m.p. 168°-70°. (Found: N, 14.40%, $C_{18}H_{15}O_2N_4S$ required: N, 14.49%).

(c) *Ethyl-4'-(2-amino-4-phenylthio-s-triazin-6-yl)-aminobenzoate* (I; $R_1 = NH_2$; $R_2 = H_5C_2OOC\ Ph.NH-$; $R_3 = S-C_6H_5$):

Liquor ammonia (50 ml.) was added to the solution of (compound I; $R_1 = Cl$; $R_2 = H_5C_2OOC\ Ph.NH-$; $R_3 = S-C_6H_5$) (18 g.) in dioxan and refluxed in water bath at 80°-85° for 1½ hr. The contents were poured in crushed ice, product was isolated as usual and crystallised from ethanol. Yield 15.0 g. (87.78%) m.p. 140°-42° (Found: N, 19.00% $C_{18}H_{17}O_2N_5S$ requires: N, 19.07%).

(d) *Ethyl-4'-(2-arylsulphonamido-4-phenylthio-s-triazin-6-yl)-aminobenzoate* (I; $R_1 = NH-SO_2-R$; $R_2 = H_5C_2OOC\ Ph.NH-$; $R_3 = S-C_6H_5$):

Compound (I; $R_1 = NH_2$; $R_2 = H_5C_2OOC\ Ph.NH-$; $R_3 = S-C_6H_5$) (0.01 mole) dissolved in acetone was added to the solution of arylsulphonyl chloride (0.01 mole) in pyridine and heated under reflux on water bath at 80°-85° for 1½ hr. The contents were poured into crushed ice and clear solution obtained was acidified by dilute hydrochloric acid (congo red). The product obtained after the addition of aqueous sodium acetate solution (10 ml.; 8%) was filtered, washed, dried and crystallised from ethanol. Physical constants of these compounds are recorded in the Table.

(e) *Ethyl-4'-(2-arylsulphonamido-4-phenylsulphonyl-s-triazin-6-yl)-aminobenzoate* (I; $R_1 = -NH-SO_2-R$; $R_2 = H_5C_2OOC\ Ph.NH-$; $R_3 = -SO_2-C_6H_5$):

Compound (I; $R_1 = -NH-SO_2-R$; $R_2 = H_5C_2OOC\ Ph.NH-$; $R_3 = S-C_6H_5$) (1 g.) was dissolved in acetone and glacial acetic acid (10 ml.). To this potassium permanganate solution (6%) was added gradually with constant stirring at room temperature till its colour persisted and kept for 3-4 hrs. The contents were decolourised by passing sulphurdioxide gas. The product obtained was poured in crushed ice, filtered, washed with cold water, dried and crystallised from ethanol. Physical constants of the compounds are recorded in the Table.

TABLE—PHYSICAL DATA OF SULPHONAMIDES OF STRUCTURE (I)

Sr. No.	R	$R_1 = NH-SO_2R$; $R_2 = H_5C_2OOC\ Ph.NH-$		$R_3 = S-C_6H_5$		$R_3 = SO_2-C_6H_5$	
		Yield %	m.p. °C	Yield %	m.p. °C	Yield %	m.p. °C
1.	Phenyl	65.34	125-27	72.73	232-34		
2.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	70.00	110-12	68.15	226-28		
3.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	60.00	105-07	65.00	195-96		
4.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	65.80	190-93	69.80	198-200		
5.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	59.00	97-98	64.00	210-12		
6.	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	68.40	108-09	68.00	190-92		
7.	<i>p</i> -Acetamidophenyl	62.30	135-37	71.00	178-80		
8.	α -Naphthyl	63.70	95-97	78.00	203-05		
9.	β -Naphthyl	57.30	100-02	80.00	186-88		

All the above compounds gave correct N analysis.

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Chemical Investigation of some Mangrove Species. Part II: *Carapa obovata* Bl.

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C. OBOVATA Bl. is a small tree with a large spherical fruit (Bengali: Dhundul). This mangrove genus *Carapa* belongs to family Meliaceae.

In our earlier report¹ we have illustrated the status of a species in a genus grown under saline soil from the studies of three mangrove species of *Avicennia* (Fam. Verbenaceae). Now we want to communicate our findings on a species, yet unexamined, of another mangrove genus *Carapa* with a view to compare the results published earlier by different workers.

Literature on genus *Carapa* revealed the presence of Deacetoxy-7-oxogedunin², Carapin³ in *C. procera* and 6 α -11 β -diacetoxy gedunin⁴, 11 β -acetoxy gedunin⁴, andirobin^{5,6}, 7-deacetoxy-7-oxogedunin^{5,6} in *C. guianensis* and gedunin⁷, xylocarpin⁷, methyl 3- β -acetoxy-1-oxomeliac-8,30-enate⁷, β -sitosterol⁷ in *Xylocarpus* (syn. *Carapa*) *granatum*. Plant material for investigation was collected from Sundarban (West Bengal).

Petroleum extract of the air dried bark was concentrated. The ether soluble portion of the petroleum extract was further separated into neutral and acidic part. The acidic part yielded no triterpene acid. The neutral fraction on chromatography over silica gel G furnished the following compounds.

The first fraction was a white crystalline solid m.p. 248°; $[\alpha] +71^\circ$; ν_{max} 1715 cm⁻¹ (carbonyl); M.S. m/e 426 (M⁺), 411 (M⁺-CH₃), 302 (cleavage of ring D at 13-18 and 14-15 bonds), 218 and 232 and 246 (species 205 with one, two and three additional carbon atom), 205, 191, 189; NMR. (δ) 0.79-1.5 (methyl and methylene protons), 2.32 (α -keto methylene); oxime m.p. 285°. The compound was reduced to a compound m.p. 268°; M.S. m/e 428 (M⁺), 413 (M⁺-CH₃), 395 (413-H₂O), 304 (cleavage of ring D), 275, 207. This mass fragmentation pattern were in complete conformity with that of epifriedelinol. All these data showed the presence of friedelin which was finally confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample. Second fraction was triacontanol, m.p. 80°.

Third fraction, a shining crystalline solid m.p. 138°, ν_{max} 3520 (hydroxyl) and 1649 cm⁻¹ (double bond), showed bluish-violet coloration with Liebermann-Burchard reagent (test for sterol). Mass spectrum of this compound registered two molecular ion peaks, one at m/e 414 and other at 412 which showed the solid to be a sterol mixture. The genesis of other peaks can be evaluated as m/e 396 (414-18) and 394 (412-18), 255 (396-C₁₀H₂₁ or 394-C₁₀H₁₉). The compound with ring double bond and saturated C₁₀H₂₁ side chain corresponding to molecular ion m/e 414 was β -sitosterol and the other one with C₁₀H₁₉ side chain was identical in all respects with stigmasterol.

Last fraction, a heavy amorphous solid, registered an intense spot at R_f 0.7 which on further purification through exhaustive preparative tlc yielded a crystalline material m.p. 290°; ν_{max} 1760 (ester carbonyl), 1715 (ring ketone), 1660 cm⁻¹ (double bond). The mass fragmentation pattern clearly indicated it to be a mixture having tetra-nortriterpene skeleton with M⁺ at m/e 542 and m/e 514. The other mass peaks were at m/e 499, 472, 470, 454, 439, 426, 411, 395, 385, 201, 187, 173. The compound was a mixture (A) of methyl 3 β -isopropyl-1-oxo-

meliacate and methyl 3 β -acetoxy-1-oxo-meliacate. NMR data on this mixture is awaiting. Due to paucity of materials a good NMR was not available. We want to report the NMR data in our subsequent papers on 'the effect of ecology on biosynthetic route'.

Petroleum extract of *C. obovata* leaves on similar treatment as previously described, yielded Friedelin, β -sitosterol, Stigmasterol and a mixture of two tetranortriterpenoids (A).

From the earlier report²⁻⁷ and also from present investigation it is evident that the biosynthetic pattern of all the species in the genus *Carapa* is somewhat uniform.

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Studies on Adsorption Indicators. Part I. Mono- and Bis-hydroxyphenyl phthalides as Adsorption Indicators in Argentometric Titrations of Iodide Ions

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THE use of phenolphthalein as adsorption indicator in slightly alkaline condition is highly recommended in literature by Uzumasa and Miyake¹.

In the present communication the studies have been extended to seven other similar and unsymmetrical phthaloids (Mono- and Bis-hydroxyphenylphthalides). Thus, 3-(*p*-hydroxyphenyl) phthalide (I), 3,3-bis(*p*-hydroxyphenyl) 4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide (II), 3-acetyl-3-(*o*- or *p*-hydroxyphenyl)4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide (III), 3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)4,5-dimethoxyphthalide (IV), 3-phenyl-3-(*o*- or *p*-hydroxyphenyl)2:3-naphthalide (V), β -1-naphthyl-phenolsuccinoin (VI), and β -2-naphthylphenolsuccinoin (VII) have been studied for their utility as adsorption indicators in the argentometric titrations of iodide ions.